

STOCKHOLM UNIVERSITY
OF THE ARTS | STOCKHOLMS
KONSTNÄRLIGA
HÖGSKOLA

PROCEEDINGS

of the 28th Annual Conference, International Sustainable Development Research Society

**Sustainable Development and Courage:
Culture, Art and Human Rights**

**Stockholm and online, Sweden
June 14-17, 2022**

Sustainable Development and Courage: Culture, Art and Human rights
28th Annual Conference, of the International Sustainable Development
Research Society
Stockholm, Sweden, June 15-17, 2022

Proceedings of abstracts, posters and papers that have been accepted
after a double blind review process in several stages.

ISBN: 978-91-89504-17-2

Publisher: Södertörn University

Publication year: 2022

Editors: Peter Dobers, Malin Gawell, Johan Gärde, Stefan Silfverskiöld

The Role of Structured Decision-making in Community-based Adaptation: A systematic scoping review

Subhashree Nath¹

¹ *Dresden Leibniz Graduate School, Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development, Faculty of Environmental Sciences, Technical University Dresden, Germany,*
s.nath@dlgs.ioer.de

Abstract

Community-based adaptation (CbA) enables communities, especially marginalised communities to adapt and build resilience to the uncertainties climate change ensues. However, there are many barriers to the successful implementation of CbA. While existing literature has synthesised evidence on the types of barriers, there is currently no published evidence synthesis on how these barriers manifest as a CbA project progresses and how it affects the process of decision-making adopted in CbA. Uncertainty remains as to how to overcome these barriers to ensure successful CbA implementation with representative decision-making. This article argues that mapping when and how these barriers manifest in the CbA project cycle will help in overcoming them by facilitating their management through structured decision-making (SDM) processes. Therefore, through a review of peer-reviewed articles selected through a systematic database search, this article systematically scopes the literature to map the identified barriers to the typical steps of a CbA project cycle and explores how structured decision-making (SDM) processes (e.g., adaptive management) provide a way to navigate the heterogeneity within communities and multiple stakeholder interests, by engaging the community and coordinating amongst multiple decision-makers, bridging different interests, information required and values.

Keywords: Community-based adaptation, structured decision-making processes, boundary objects

1. Introduction

While the impacts of climate change are being felt in every part of the world, the poor and marginalised people, for example, those living in slums and informal settlements, are more exposed to these impacts and are predisposed to be adversely affected due to their socioeconomic and built environment conditions. For instance, slums are exposed to higher local temperatures as compared to other parts of the city, owing to high building density, poor roofing materials and limited open space and vegetation (Mehrotra et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2019). Further, these communities are often the last to receive the

benefits of any development or adaptation initiatives, due to their disputed legal identity (as in the case of slums) along with insufficient governance capacities and/or political will, (Satterthwaite et al., 2020). In case the government does take action, limited financial and human resources lead them to focus on reactive management and technical fixes, instead of long-term proactive approaches to climate adaptation (Measham et al., 2011 as cited in Spires et al., 2014). In addition, climate change is only one of the many challenges marginalised communities face and hence, it is unlikely that initiatives and interventions with the sole agenda of climate adaptation will reflect community priorities (Reid et al., 2009, p. 13). In such contexts, community¹-based adaptation (CbA) is gaining traction, which frames adaptation as a continuum, that extends between development and adaptation (Heltberg et al., 2012, p. 150; McGray et al., 2007) strengthening resilience through development (Ayers & Forsyth, 2009; Ensor et al., 2018). It is a type of adaptation (i.e. adjustment in natural or human systems in response to actual or expected climatic stimuli or their effects which moderates harm or exploits beneficial opportunities (IPCC, 2018)) that operates at the community level and focuses specifically on the empowerment of the community, ‘helping people to help themselves’ (Warrick, 2009).

CbA approaches focus on empowerment and the development process rather than only on specific adaptation interventions. This brings adaptive capacity and hence, the ‘capacity of the actors in the system to influence resilience’ (Walker et al., 2004) to the centre of CbA (Ensor et al., 2018). CbA has the potential to harness the ability to adapt by emphasising knowledge transfer and integration, focusing on ‘not what is being done at the community level, but why, and with what knowledge – or, more specifically, whose knowledge’ (Ayers & Huq, 2013, p. 212 as cited in Kirkby et al., 2017).

However, given the complexity of the problems and the need for systemic changes to truly address them, CbA is emphasised as part of the solution, one component of an integrated set of responses including natural resource management, disaster risk reduction, poverty reduction, ecosystem-based adaptation and sustainable development (Allen, 2006; Archer et al., 2014; Dodman et al., 2010). The success of a CbA project lies in representative participation in the decision-making processes, which has the potential to enrich the resilience of communities, as they become more informed, learn from each other and mutual trust is fostered (Evers et al., 2018). But this is challenging to achieve given the heterogeneous nature of communities resulting from local power structures, as well as communication barriers, lack of awareness and locally relevant, accessible and comprehensible

¹ Community-based adaptation in this paper refers specifically to communities of place, i.e. ties to a geographical location (Duane, 1997 as cited in (Clissold and McNamara, 2020)

information to base their decision on. These represent a bulk of barriers to a successful implementation of CbA. Barriers are defined as factors, conditions or obstacles that reduce the effectiveness of adaptation strategies (Hunage et al., 2011; Moser & Ekstrom, 2010 as cited in Antwi-Agyei et al., 2015). If barriers are not understood and overcome, they become limits (Piggott-McKellar et al., 2019), defined as ‘conditions or factors that render adaptation ineffective as a response to climate change and are largely insurmountable’ (Adger et al., 2007, p. 733).

Figure 1 Conceptual framework: Drawing parallels between CbA project steps (adapted from CARE 2010) & adaptive management cycle

These represent a bulk of barriers to a successful implementation of CbA. Barriers are defined as factors, conditions or obstacles that reduce the effectiveness of adaptation strategies (Hunage et al., 2011; Moser & Ekstrom, 2010 as cited in Antwi-Agyei et al., 2015). If barriers are not understood and overcome, they become limits (Piggott-McKellar et al., 2019), defined as ‘conditions or factors that render adaptation ineffective as a response to climate change and are largely insurmountable’ (Adger et al., 2007, p. 733).

To overcome barriers, researchers have stressed on the importance of identifying barriers, understanding the conditions that create these barriers and how they operate (Antwi-Agyei et al., 2015; Spires et al., 2014). While there are precedents of systematic literature reviews of both peer-reviewed articles (Antwi-Agyei et al., 2015; McNamara & Buggy, 2017; Spires et al., 2014) and reviews of grey literature (Piggott-McKellar et al., 2019) where barriers were identified, there is currently no published evidence synthesis on how these barriers manifest as a CbA project progresses and the process of decision-making adopted in CbA. Uncertainty remains as to how to

overcome these barriers to ensure successful CbA implementation with representative decision-making.

To address this, this article systematically scopes the literature to map the identified barriers to the typical steps of a CbA project cycle (Figure 1) which consists of four iterative phases (CARE, 2010). Section 3.2 discusses these phases and the barriers encountered in detail. We illustrate that mapping these barriers to the CbA process is a step towards overcoming them by structuring the decision-making processes in CbA by informing when and how these barriers emerge. The article further explores how structured decision-making (SDM) processes (e.g., adaptive management) provide a way to navigate the heterogeneity of vulnerabilities and multiple stakeholder interests, by engaging the community and coordinating amongst multiple decision-makers, bridging various involved organisations, defining a clear community objective, and planning with long decision horizons (Allen et al., 2011; Chacko et al., 2018). Thereby, acting as a boundary object. Boundary objects connect various actors through a common interface for communication (Star & Griesemer, 1989) and help to bridge competing values (Willems et al., 2022). Such a boundary object can facilitate the community's ability to adapt by identifying the role various actors, stakeholders and organisations play at each step of the CbA project cycle, along with information-knowledge requirements and governance support required at respective steps. This article aims to build the foundation for such a boundary object. To do so, it answers the following questions:

- a) What are the barriers encountered in different stages of a typical CbA project cycle?
- b) What is known about the decision-making process involved in a CbA project?
- c) How does structured decision-making (SDM) facilitate CbA?

The next section provides an overview of the steps taken to retrieve and analyse literature systematically and introduces the typology of barriers used to analyse the literature. The results and discussion section first reports on the key characteristics of the literature analysed and then discusses the research questions in light of the knowledge synthesised from the literature. The last section suggests future research pathways to apply the knowledge gathered for enabling future CbA projects.

2. Methods

Scoping reviews are exploratory evidence synthesis projects that take a descriptive approach to systematically chart the literature available on a topic, identifying key concepts, theories, sources of evidence and gaps in the research (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005; Sargeant & O'Connor, 2020). In this paper, a systematic scoping review is used to investigate how the barriers identified through the review

operate at different stages of a CbA project cycle. The process followed for the scoping review involved selecting and analysing peer-reviewed literature, based on the PRISMA guidelines for scoping reviews (PRISMA-ScR) (Tricco et al., 2018) While the author acknowledges that many CbA project implementation and evaluation reports are documented in grey literature, due to feasibility issues and lack of information in the format and detail sought in this review, grey literature has not been directly covered.

The following steps were followed for the systematic scoping review:

2.1 Document identification and selection

Documents were identified through a keyword search in the two databases: Web of Science and Scopus in August 2021. These databases were selected due to their extensive and current coverage of interdisciplinary peer-reviewed literature. The following keywords were derived from a preliminary search based on the research question(s): "community", "adaptation", "resilience", "community-based adaptation", "urban", "heat", "drought", "climate change", "decision", "decision-making", "enablers", "barriers". These were then classified to form a literature search logic grid: Focus, Assessment, Scale, Subject, Systems perspective (FAS3) derived from PICO (Population, Intervention, Comparison Intervention/ concept/ context, Outcome measures). This logic grid was used to develop an iterative search strategy where queries were various combinations of the categories as shown in Table 1. This helped in documenting change in search results (both in quantity and quality) as queries moved from a wide focus on urban CbA and decision-making (Iteration 1: Scale + Assessment + Subject) to a narrower query which included the specific subject of adaptation and/ resilience to heat and drought (Iteration 4: Assessment + Focus + Scale + Subject + System). For instance, although the initial idea for the search queries was to narrow the selection of articles to CbA to “heat” and “drought” (Subject) and “urban” (Scale) communities, the lack of quality results led to a widening of the inclusion to any human settlement and adaptation to general climate change.

Table 1. FAS3 logic grid for planning and documenting search queries

Focus	Assessment	Scale	Subject	Systems perspective
“decision”	“enablers”	“urban”	“heat”	“resilience”
“decision-making”	“barriers”	“community”	“drought”	“adaptation”
	“effective”	“community-based”		
	“requirement”	“neighbourhood”		
	“successful”			
	“drivers”			

Articles identified from each query were collated in Excel to remove duplicates. A total of 2307 unique articles were identified and uploaded to Rayyan (Ouzzani et al., 2016) for the title and abstract screening. Rayyan, a free web and mobile application, was used to expedite initial screening. Rayyan projects are accessible to multiple team members, making the screening process transparent and accountable. Exclusion criteria were tiered (Figure 2), ensuring that only articles that discuss human settlement community-based climate change adaptation were assessed for barriers, enablers and decision-making steps within the project cycle. Initial exclusion criteria removed articles that were not about climate change adaptation, not about human community, broad-scale adaptation (e.g. regional, national) and articles which were focused on policy and governance. After the first round of exclusion, 157 articles were selected which went through another round of eligibility checks by full-text screening (Figure 2). Articles that did not discuss community-led (climate change) adaptation, i.e., either they had a community/ neighbourhood scale but adaptation was ‘done’ to the community by an external agency or it dealt only with development, were excluded. Following this, 46 articles were selected for full-text reading. An additional 34 articles were also selected, that were found manually or through snowballing references cited in the 46 selected articles. A third exclusion round where articles that although were about CbA but do not discuss barriers, challenges to or enablers of CbA, nor mention any implemented case study to deduce these from, were excluded. 40 articles were finally selected for data extraction and mapping.

2.2 Document Analysis

The first step in the analysis of selected articles (n=40) was to categorise the identified barriers. Previous typologies of barriers ranged from classifications such as in Antwi-Agyei et al., (2015): financial, socio-cultural (incl. cognitive & normative barriers), institutional and technological barriers, to broader conceptual grouping as in Spires et al., (2014): social, resource and physical barriers.

Emphasising the causal relationship of barriers, this paper suggests two broad domains: the socio-political-cultural-economic domain(S) and the technological/infrastructure domain (T) (Table 2).

This clustering is derived inductively from the selected articles based on the causal relationship between the barriers: barriers which often manifested together were classified under the same domain. Among others, Domain S includes barriers related to local power structure resulting from cultural and religious norms, gender norms, and socio-economic status and leading to power imbalances and selective participation of community members in decision-making. While all of these barriers could be classified as power imbalances, they have been disaggregated as cultural and religious norms, gender norms and inter/intra-community power imbalances. These have been given a particular focus as they are well-established contexts of marginalisation and are some of the critical underlying causes of vulnerability. For example, a UNDP-Global Environment Facility programme on CbA recognises that ‘without an express consideration of gender from the very beginning of the project cycle, the choice of adaptation interventions can have unintended gender implications’ (UNDP, 2010, p.39 as cited in Dodman and Mitlin, 2013). Barriers related to domain S affect both the initiation and permanency of adaptation actions and are critical in influencing the conversion of adaptive capacity to adaptation actions (Adger et al., 2009; Grothmann & Patt, 2005 as cited in Spires et al., 2014).

Domain T includes barriers related to the built environment of the community and associated infrastructure like public transportation networks, information communication networks, as well their management. Table 2 enumerates the barriers identified under each domain. Clarify seemingly overlapping barriers.

Figure 2 Summary diagram of the search strategy and review steps taken (Refer to Appendix 1 for the selected articles)

Table 2. STS typology of barriers classification

	(S) Socio-political-cultural-economic domain		(T) Technological/ Infrastructure domain
1	Lack of motivation in community to engage	20	Lack of institutional skills/ capacity
2	Lack of meaningful participation	21	Lack of coordination among institutions
3	Lack of awareness (related to climate change and adaptation pathways)	22	Lack of relevant available info.
4	Lack of community skills/capacity (to comprehend information, evaluate decisions, take and monitor actions)	23	Lack of comprehensible info.
5	Lack of trust btw comm., facilitators & donors	24	Lack of infra. provision/ maintenance
6	Lack of knowledge transfer & integration	25	Lack of ICT
7	Communication/ language barriers	26	Lack of adaptable technology
8	Lack of consensus		
9	Gender norms		
10	Cultural & religious norms		
11	Power imbalances		
12	Lack of sense of project ownership		
13	Lack of time/ patience		
14	Tenure rights		
15	Policy gaps		
16	Unresponsive/ inefficient/ biased governance		
17	Lack of human resources		
18	Lack of reliable &/ long-term financing		
19	Donor requirements/ expectations		

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Selected documents

The final list of articles selected for the systematic scoping review included those which discuss the barriers, enablers and challenges to CbA at a conceptual level (Dodman & Mitlin, 2013; Regmi et al., 2016) and ones which discuss the implementation of CbA and the barriers to and enablers of successful implementation. The second set of articles was the main focus, especially the ones which explained these through case studies. 29 articles or nearly three fourth of the articles selected mention case studies (Figure 3), most of which are located in countries in the global south.

However, of these 29, only 7 articles describe the implementation process. Although the majority of the selected articles and general literature on CbA emphasise the role of collective decision-making (e.g. (Galvin, 2019; Roy, 2018; Simane & Zaitchik, 2014)) for successful CbA, none of the articles explicitly mention how decision-making is integrated with the implementation process. This ubiquitous emphasis on collective decision-making but the contradictory lack of evidence on how it is addressed during the CbA implementation highlights a crucial gap in research. This article through the inductive analysis of selected articles addresses this, by first mapping the barriers encountered at each step of the CbA project

cycle and then, discussing the decision-making process.

Figure 3 Location of CbA case studies discussed in 29 articles (out of 40)(Refer to Appendix 1 for the articles)

Figure 4: Bar chart showing the no. of articles mentioning different barriers to CbA (barriers under domain S are in pink and barriers under domain T in blue)

3.2 What are the barriers encountered in different stages of a typical CbA project cycle?

Barriers were derived from the selected articles and classified under domain S (socio-political- cultural-economic domain) and domain T (technological/infrastructure domain). Figure 4 provides an overview of the frequency in which these barriers were mentioned in the articles reviewed. For instance, barriers related to domain S were most mentioned, along with a lack of information availability and relevance (domain T). This is consistent with other reviews (Antwi-Agyei et al., 2015; McNamara and Buggy, 2017; Spire et al., 2014), where social barriers were the most reported.

Among the barriers classified under domain S, no. of papers reporting on intra- and inter-community power imbalances were the highest. It is closely tied to gender, cultural and religious norms. In Figure 5, a matrix illustrates how various barriers operate at various stages of the CbA cycle. This matrix was inductively derived from the literature reviewed and illustrates the steps which are particularly challenging as well as how few barriers manifest in clusters. It was found that some barriers like lack of trust between involved parties, lack of knowledge transfer, communication barriers; lack of meaningful participation, power imbalances, gender norms, and cultural and religious norms, appear frequently and in clusters. Barriers from domain T are particularly more active in the M&E phase.

The following subsections are categorised as per the different project phases (Figure 1) and explain how

different barriers (italicised) influence each other and hence, the success of each step along the project cycle.

Figure 5: Mapping the occurrence of various barriers at different steps on the CbA project cycle (barriers under domain S are in pink and barriers under domain T in blue)

3.2.1 Barriers encountered during the analysis phase

Project analysis is the first phase, where the goal is to learn about the context of the project and its

socio-political and climate context. One of the crucial steps in this phase and the entire CbA process is defining the problem with the community. However, this is difficult to achieve in its true sense as several barriers are faced, starting with *motivating the community to engage*, especially in adaptation activities which are time-consuming with no immediate result, and when there is *a lack of time and patience*. Ensuring *meaningful participation*-where voices of all the various social groups within a community are heard, equally valued and incorporated, could become a barrier due to multiple reasons. For example, apathy to climate change adaptation especially if the community had no first-hand experience of major CC impacts (Roberts, 2010 as cited in Spires et al., 2014). Another recurrent driver of barriers is local power structures, which are at the heart of climate change vulnerability (Reid et al., 2009), resulting in *power imbalances, gender norms, and culture & religious norms* which significantly affect *meaningful participation*. A lack of involvement on the part of residents may also reflect a *lack of awareness* about pathways for participation and a *lack of capacity/skills* to self-organise (Guardaro et al., 2020). *Lack of trust* in the external facilitators also inhibits the community from sharing their problems while the perceived expertise of facilitators inhibits *knowledge transfer* to include local knowledge (Westoby et al., 2020). Along with assessing vulnerability, it is crucial to assess the strengths of the community and learn about the existing coping measures. *Communication barriers* like finding a common language to explain the issues the community is facing is a common barrier. Similarly, climate scientists find it difficult to communicate complex science and build capacity at the local level, and therefore information distributed about climate risk may fail to adequately inform the community or persuade them to respond to consequences (Harvatt et al. 2011 as cited in Khan, 2017). *Lack of comprehensible and relevant information at the community scale* are also barriers to integrating scientific information which is crucial for informing the decision-making process throughout the CbA project cycle. This also contributes to *lack of awareness and lack of capacity/skills*.

3.2.2 Barriers faced in the planning phase

The second phase is the planning phase, which begins with designing a strategy to ensure participation, making sure that the voices of the most vulnerable are heard and included in establishing the project scope and objective. However, planning meaningful participation and sustaining it throughout the project term, is one of the major challenges in CbA implementation. As Ayers and Forsyth (2009), Dodman and Mitlin (2013) and Regmi et al., (2016) state, simply organising participatory exercises does not necessarily empower vulnerable households and groups, nor does it guarantee participation (Kim & Kang, 2018). Facilitators must understand local power relations and plan participation and engagement accordingly (Regmi et al., 2016). Therefore, *power imbalances, gender norms, and*

cultural norms remain major barriers to planning participation, along with *motivating the community*, *lack of trust*, and *communication barriers*.

Tenure rights also influence participation as members with short or unsure tenure might not see any benefit in engaging in long-term adaptation benefits. It also influences the decision on project scope, with short-term measures favoured by those with no or temporary tenure rights. Particularly in the case of informal settlements, tenure plays a crucial role where lack of legal tenure rights leads to a *lack of trust* in external facilitators, fearing eviction. However in case, representative participation is achieved, the next barrier is the *lack of knowledge transfer and integration*, where the local participants are not considered co-decision-makers and have tokenistic involvement to choose from pre-decided options. *Time and patience* are also major barriers since a participatory approach takes longer compared to other adaptation approaches (Kim and Kang, 2018) which might not be acceptable to donors or feasible for the community.

Participation planning and implementation also require substantial *institutional capacity*, requiring time and human resources, which often becomes a barrier. In addition, *lack of access to information and communication (ICT)* at this stage slows down the dissemination of information in the community.

At the stage of defining the objective and scope of the project, *lack of consensus* is a barrier as reaching consensus among diverse actors, stakeholders and donors is a challenge (Chacko et al., 2018). Locals need to understand the objectives of a project and the reasons why it is beneficial to adopt certain measures and trade others. *Lack of awareness* in such cases is a barrier to defining the scope, in addition to a *lack of community's skills and capacities* to identify trade-offs. *Lack of relevant, accessible and comprehensible information* adds to this. For instance, understanding the science and drivers behind climate impacts, for example, urban heat, hinder the residents from comprehending how increased urban heat was impacting their health, quality of life, and personal economic situation, therefore, influencing their decision not only on what measures to choose, the trade-offs or the outcomes but on the necessity or possibility of any adaptation at all (Guardaro et al., 2020). This also stems from *communication barriers* between climate scientists and the general public.

In addition, during the steps of defining project scope, evaluation criteria, identifying trade-offs, the *availability of reliable/long-term financing* and *donor requirements* are two major barriers. Donor restrictions and guidelines often attempt to dictate how projects should be implemented while a lack of long-term financing is a barrier to the sustainability of CbA projects (Westoby et al., 2020). The development-adaptation continuum approach of CbA is also a challenge when existing pathways for adaptation financing stress that CbA activities must singularly respond to climate change (Dodman

and Mitlin, 2013), which often is not possible in the most marginalised and vulnerable communities, where adaptation is only possible through development.

Estimating outcomes requires a clear visualisation of likely scenarios, the benefits and disadvantages of each measure, and time and cost implications. Without developing easy-to-comprehend visualisation techniques and awareness generation, residents often fail to see a solution pathway, or the threshold of response need and feasibility (Guardaro et al., 2020). Kim and Kang (2018) suggest that scenario planning can be applied to the community planning process for visualising climate change information, depicting likely outcomes and therefore facilitating the identification of capacity and resource requirements. At this stage, *lack of community skills, lack of trust, knowledge transfer and clear communication* are major barriers, in addition to *institutional capacity, and lack of relevant and comprehensible information*.

The final step of this phase is deciding on the interventions or strategy, which must be taken through a transparent process, taking stock of all social groups. A major barrier to this step is the *lack of consensus*, balancing immediate problems against a strategic, longer-term perspective (Few, Brown & Tompkins (2007) as cited in Archer et al., 2014). It is unlikely that all stakeholders will unanimously support any prospective adaptation measures (Kirkby et al., 2015). It is a major challenge to moderate different and possibly conflicting goals of stakeholders, some of which will be dependent on their roles in the process (Balcik, et al., 2010; Chacko, 2015 as cited in Chacko et al., 2018). *Lack of meaningful participation, motivating the community to engage*, integrating local knowledge into the decision (*knowledge transfer*), *power imbalances*, and *gender roles* dictated by *cultural norms* restricting women's involvement in the process, all influence the final decision. This is aggravated by a *lack of institutional capacity and readily available comprehensible and relevant information*.

3.2.3 Barriers faced in the implementation phase

Project implementation is the third phase, where the effectiveness of the project is ensured by establishing a transparent accountability method and clarifying the roles and responsibilities of all involved. Barriers faced during this phase include *motivating the community to engage*, ensuring *meaningful participation and generating a sense of ownership* among the community members and local authorities. If local participation and priorities that reflect people's needs and wishes are not part of the implementation plan, the community might not identify with the project and take ownership of the initiative (Remling & Veitayaki, 2016), leading to a *lack of sense of ownership*. For permanent and long-term interventions, *tenure rights* could be a determining factor and a barrier. It affects the

willingness to share maintenance responsibility or cost for interventions in common areas as well as rented properties (Guardaro et al., 2020). In the case of local authorities also, *a lack of sense of (project) ownership* may lead to failure in providing technical and financial resources to implement the adaptation plan (Regmi & Star, 2014). Bureaucratic rules and procedures as well as ambiguous mandates from superiors within an institution, *lack of coordination among involved institutions* and therefore *inefficient governance* is also a barrier to the implementation phase (Antwi-Agyei et al., 2015). Implementation might also fail due to failure in completely realising the ideas of self-governance that CbA projects tend to instil, because of *policy gaps* and limits placed on the devolution of authority, funding and other resources (Gautam & Pokharel, 2011 as cited in (Regmi and Star, 2014). Similarly, various local legislations might also be barriers, although the literature review doesn't make any statement on this. *Policy gaps* also lead to a *lack of coordination between involved institutions at different administrative levels and actors*, causing ineffective partnership and sustainability of CbA projects (Berquist, Daniere, and Drummond 2014; Middelbeek, Kollé, and Verrest 2014 as cited in Piggott-McKellar et al., 2019). Without a commitment to integrate CbA into national policy and planning with a commitment to dedicate resources to the local level, there is a risk that climate finance will continue to support top-down, centralised activities that may struggle to address the needs of vulnerable communities (Remling and Veitayaki, 2016), resulting in *lack of reliable/ long-term financing*.

Developing the capacity of the actors for successful implementation depends on good *communication skills* which remains a barrier due to a *lack of institutional capacity*. Scepticism raised by *gender, cultural and traditional norms* can also be a barrier to the adoption of new information and technologies required for implementation, especially if there are no preceding successful pilot cases and new practices fail (Spires et al., 2014). *The lack of locally adaptable technology* is also a barrier since communities can only employ the adaptation tools and options that have been developed, and which are applicable in the local context (Antwi-Agyei et al., 2015). These are further aggravated by *donor requirements* since developing the capacity of the local community might not be defined as a direct contribution to adaptation, especially in the absence of means to quantify capacity development and how it contributed to adaptation.

3.2.4 Barriers faced during the monitoring and evaluation (M&E) phase

Once the project is implemented, the monitoring and evaluation (M&E) phase checks the effectiveness of the actions taken and assesses areas of improvement. In this phase, the focus is on learning from the actions taken in previous phases, leading to rounds of feedback to ensure better and

equitable planning and implementation in subsequent rounds. Technical barriers like *knowledge and information management, required infrastructure provision/ maintenance, coordination among various institutional members, and timely and relevant information* availability are dominant in M&E. Access to suitable *information & communication technology (ICT)* could also become a barrier, for instance when information transfer is restricted due to a lack of access to smartphones or internet coverage. The M&E phase might often focus on demonstrating value for money and results of the interventions, instead of focusing on learning and feedback due to *donor requirements* (Faulkner et al., 2015) influencing how the projects are monitored and evaluated, for upward accountability purposes, in line with the information needs of funding agencies. In addition, a *lack of human resources* is a key barrier in establishing M&E due to varied and detailed data collection requirements. Owing to the *limited capacities of institutional staff, and lack of community skills*, project outcomes are often not sufficiently recorded and consequently limit the effective evaluation of projects in identifying lessons learnt (Piggott-McKellar et al., 2019). Further, if a participatory M&E is not ensured, for instance, due to *power imbalances, gender norms, cultural norms, the lack of trust, communication and knowledge transfer/integration* among the community members, inhibits information and skills transfer, which is crucial for initiating learning and facilitating self-organisation in the face of emergencies and uncertainties.

3.3 What is known about the decision-making process involved in a CbA project?

Of the 40 selected articles, while 7 articles discuss the implementation process, none discussed the decision-making process behind the CbA implementation. However, that CbA projects should empower the community to make decisions about adaptation themselves, has been reiterated by various authors like Dodman and Mitlin (2013, p. 3), who emphasised the criticality of ensuring residents' involvement and engagement in the decision-making processes involving their local areas. Fox et al., (2021, p. 8) mention that top-down decision-making processes often result in negative implications for the community, while describing the case of informal settlements in Cape Town, South Africa. Rashid & Khan (2013) emphasises the long-term and uncertain nature of climate change which makes top-down planning adaptation plans unviable since they cannot plan for a 30-50 years spectrum. Therefore, without the development of collective decision-making capacity, the community will always be dependent on external support, which is difficult to get in marginalised communities.

Rather than external actors predetermining solutions, which is common in top-down adaptation planning, CbA must capacitate communities to shape adaptation interventions, recognising local communities' essential roles in the process of assessing climate and environmental risks, as well as in

planning, implementing, and the monitoring and evaluating of actions (CARE, 2010; Dumar, 2010; Remling & Veitayaki, 2016). Therefore, ‘community-driven decision-making blended with scientific predictions on the impacts of climate change’ (Roy, 2018, p. 6) is one of the salient features of the CbA project.

While the literature reviewed doesn’t chart a clear process for decision-making, the following steps were found critical in facilitating collective decision-making:

- The initial steps of the CbA project must include thorough interaction with the community to learn not only about their challenges aggravated by climate change but also their coping mechanisms
- Exclusion of certain groups from the decision-making process is inevitable in a community-driven decision-making process due to a variety of power relations, gender roles, and cultural and traditional norms. Therefore, existing community-decision making processes must be analysed, misrepresentation noted and the disadvantages communicated to the community.
- Climate change awareness workshops facilitate informed decision-making. Such workshops also form part of the initial steps and should ideally be conducted before or during the project planning phase.
- Awareness generation about the CbA process is critical to ensure inclusive participation and sustained engagement of the community, as well as securing long-term funding. Awareness about the process might positively affect the motivation of the community to engage in a time intensive process and resolve conflict with donor requirements of immediate results.
- Information needs and accountability requirements for various stakeholders must be identified. Gathering accurate and relevant information is a key necessity to inform local decision-making processes.

Based on the CbA adaptation toolkit developed by CARE (2010) and integrating the above-mentioned points, a set of guiding questions is suggested in Table 3, pairing diagnostic questions with each step of the CbA implementation process.

Table 3. Guiding questions to facilitate decision-making throughout the CbA implementation process

S. No	CbA Process Steps	Guiding questions
1	Define the problem with the community	Who defines the problem? Who influences problem framing?
2	Analyse climate context	What are the community observations/perceptions of CC?
3	Assess vulnerability	Which social groups are most vulnerable? Who has access to & control over common resources?
4	Assess multilevel policy & national framework	Which are the key institutions? What are relevant policies & plans?
5	Assess strengths	What are the existing coping measures?
6	Plan participation	Are the voices of the most vulnerable & marginalised heard? How is equitable participation of women ensured?
7	Define the project scope	What are the community adaptation/ development priorities? Who is financing?
8	Define evaluation criteria	What are the community decided goals across spatial & temporal scales?
9	Identify trade-offs	What are the potential harms and benefits to different social groups within the community?
10	Estimate outcomes	What are the expected results realistically achievable?
11	Identify capacity/resource requirements	What community/ institutional capacities are required? What are the human/information/ knowledge/ financial resources required?
12	Decide	Is the final decision-making process transparent & participatory?
13	Plan effective implementation	What are the monthly/ annual goals?
14	Ensure effective partnerships	What are the roles & responsibilities of each actor & stakeholder? How is accountability maintained between all stakeholders?
15	Develop the capacity of actors	Which capacity development requirements need to be prioritised and acted on?
16	Establish a monitoring & evaluation process	Do the community & partners have the necessary capacity to monitor & evaluate? What are the evaluation criteria?
17	Emergency preparedness	What are the criteria to adjust the project approach in case of an emergency?

3.4 How does structured decision-making (SDM) facilitate CbA?

A decision-making process suitable for community-based adaptation projects must address the involvement of multiple decision-makers, defining a clear community objective and planning with a long decision horizon (Chacko et al., 2018). Frameworks used in structured decision-making

processes are designed to enable self-organisation, transparent and accountable decision-making, in the face of uncertainties in future climate change and its impacts. Using tools like models to illustrate uncertainties and demonstrate trade-offs (Nay et al., 2014) or simulation models to estimate the consequences of actions (Power, 2002), they provide an overview of different adaptation pathways and/or emergency coping measures, with trade-offs and benefits highlighted, ensuring periodic reevaluation to facilitate strategy development even as systems are being impacted by ongoing climate change. When these decisions are made by the community, these frameworks also work as checks and balances to avoid power abuse and elite capture, ensuring that the voices of every community group are considered and benefits equally shared. With the adoption of SDM in CbA processes, learning through ad hoc trial and error, which is common in autonomous coping strategies of communities, is replaced with learning by careful design and testing ((Walters, 1997 as cited in Williams, 2011).

Further, SDM processes like adaptive management when integrated with the CbA process will provide an opportunity to learn not only about the adaptation measures but also about the decision process itself (Williams, 2011). This is very crucial in communities where the decision process is influenced by power imbalances within the community and between affected communities, gender, culture and religious norms, along with influences from external facilitators, government and non- governmental organisations. In such cases, SDM processes also provide a way to navigate the heterogeneity and multiple stakeholder interests, by engaging the community and coordinating amongst multiple decision-makers, bridging various involved organisations (Allen et al., 2011; Chacko et al., 2018). Therefore, SDM processes act as a boundary object, where decision-makers of varied backgrounds, worldviews, expectations and interests can cooperate and communicate in a standardised interface that acts as a common language (Star & Griesemer, 1989). Boundary objects can be both material or product (a tool, maps, models, shared infrastructure) and conceptual or the process itself (procedural instructions, frameworks)(Star & Griesemer, 1989; Steger et al., 2018, pp. 154-155, as cited in Willems et al., 2022). Therefore, SDM can facilitate CbA in two ways. First, by creating a process, which ensures transparency and accessibility to all stakeholders, ensuring and facilitating their commitment to a process for adjusting strategies over time, based on M&E status and learnings (Williams et al., 2009). Second, as a supporting tool which collects and processes information into actionable knowledge, creates a portfolio of acceptable outcomes of each adaptation measure, paired with trade-offs, cost-benefit analysis, the time required to implement and time required to benefit from the process, thereby creating an objective pathway of reaching consensus in the presence of multiple decision-makers.

4. Conclusions

Despite CbA's potential in enabling communities, especially marginalised communities, to adapt and build resilience to the uncertainties climate change ensues, there is still a relative scarcity of implementation of CbA interventions. This article adds to the existing literature reviews which highlight the barriers contributing to the lack of adoption of CbA practices. It also furthers the conversation on overcoming these barriers by mapping them to the typical steps of a CbA project cycle. The resultant matrix makes the interconnection of various barriers explicit. Therefore, we argue that knowing when and how these barriers emerge can help in overcoming them by facilitating their management through SDM. In general, there is a predominance of barriers related to the power structure, like power imbalances, gender norms, cultural and religious norms, and lack of community participation, highlighting the embeddedness of CbA in existing institutions of social, cultural and traditional norms, which could lead to a failure in addressing broader structural issues, power and social relation. Therefore, we suggest a set of diagnostic questions for each step based on the barriers and what is already known about the characteristics of the decision-making process adopted in CbA practices. Further, we explore the role of SDM processes in facilitating the CbA process by acting as a boundary object – both as a product and a process. Future research must explore such a boundary object that would help in multi-way communication and knowledge transfer, providing an enabling environment for the community to develop its adaptive capacity while challenging existing power structures with transparent and accountable, collective decision-making.

References

- Adger, W. N., Agrawala, S., Mirza, M. M. Q., Conde, C., O'Brien, K., Pulhin, J., Pulwarty, R., Smit, B., Takahashi, K., Enright, B., Fankhauser, S., Ford, J., Gigli, S., Jetté-Nantel, S., Klein, R. J. T., Pearce, T. D., Shreshtha, A., Shukla, P. R., Smith, J. B., ... Magalhães, A. R. (2007). Assessment of adaptation practices, options, constraints and capacity. In *Climate change 2007: Impacts adaptation and vulnerability. Contribution of working group II to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. (p. 28).
- Allen, K. M. (2006). Community-based disaster preparedness and climate adaptation: Local capacity-building in the Philippines. *Disasters*, 30(1), 81–101. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9523.2006.00308.x>
- Antwi-Agyei, P., Dougill, A. J., & Stringer, L. C. (2015). Barriers to climate change adaptation: Evidence from northeast Ghana in the context of a systematic literature review. *Climate and Development*, 7(4), 297–309. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2014.951013>
- Archer, D., Almansi, F., DiGregorio, M., Roberts, D., Sharma, D., & Syam, D. (2014). Moving towards inclusive urban adaptation: Approaches to integrating community-based adaptation to climate change at city and national scale. *Climate and Development*, 6(4), 345–356. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2014.918868>
- Arksey, H., & O'Malley, L. (2005). Scoping studies: Towards a methodological framework. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 8(1), 19–32. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1364557032000119616>
- Ayers, J., & Forsyth, T. (2009). Community-Based Adaptation to Climate Change. *Environment:*

Science and Policy for Sustainable Development, 51(4), 22–31. <https://doi.org/10.3200/ENV.51.4.22-31>

CARE. (2010). *Community Based Adaptation Toolkit*.

https://www.betterevaluation.org/en/resources/climate_change_adaptation/community_adaptation_toolkit

Dodman, D., & Mitlin, D. (2013). Challenges for Community-Based Adaptation: Discovering the Potential for Transformation. *Journal of International Development*, 25(5), 640–659.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/jid.1772>

Dodman, D., Mitlin, D., & Co, J. R. (2010). Victims to victors, disasters to opportunities: Community-driven responses to climate change in the Philippines. *International Development Planning Review*, 32(1), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.3828/idpr.2009.10>

Dumaru, P. (2010). Community-based adaptation: Enhancing community adaptive capacity in Druadrua Island, Fiji. *WIREs Climate Change*, 1(5), 751–763. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.65>

Ensor, J. E., Park, S. E., Attwood, S. J., Kaminski, A. M., & Johnson, J. E. (2018). Can community-based adaptation increase resilience? *Climate and Development*, 10(2), 134–151.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2016.1223595>

Evers, M., Almoradie, A., & de Brito, M. M. (2018). Enhancing Flood Resilience Through Collaborative Modelling and Multi-criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA). In A. Fekete & F. Fiedrich (Eds.), *Urban Disaster Resilience and Security: Addressing Risks in Societies* (pp. 221–236). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-68606-6_14

Faulkner, L., Ayers, J., & Huq, S. (2015). Meaningful Measurement for Community-Based Adaptation. *New Directions for Evaluation*, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ev.20133>

Fox, A., Ziervogel, G., & Scheba, S. (2021). Strengthening community-based adaptation for urban transformation: Managing flood risk in informal settlements in Cape Town. *Local Environment*.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2021.1923000>

Galvin, M. (2019). Making Community-Based Adaptation a Reality: Different Conceptualisations, Different Politics. *Human Geography*, 12(1), 50–63. <https://doi.org/10.1177/194277861901200104>

Guardaro, M., Messerschmidt, M., Hondula, D. M., Grimm, N. B., & Redman, C. L. (2020). Building community heat action plans story by story: A three neighborhood case study. *Cities*, 107, 102886.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2020.102886>

Heltberg, R., Gitay, H., & Prabhu, R. G. (2012). Community-based adaptation: Lessons from a grant competition. *Climate Policy*, 12(2), 143–163. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2011.582344>

IPCC. (2018). Annex I: Glossary. In J. Matthews (Ed.), *Global Warming of 1.5°C. An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the threat of climate change, sustainable development, and efforts to eradicate poverty*.

<https://www.ipcc.ch/sr15/chapter/glossary/>

Khan, A. S. (2017). COREDAR for Cities: Developing a Capacity Building Tool for Sea-Level Rise Risk Communication and Urban Community-Based Adaptation. In W. Leal Filho & J. M. Keenan (Eds.), *Climate Change Adaptation in North America: Fostering Resilience and the Regional Capacity to Adapt* (pp. 137–157). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-53742-9_9

Kim, D., & Kang, J. E. (2018). Integrating climate change adaptation into community planning using a participatory process: The case of Saebat Maeul community in Busan, Korea. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, 45(4), 669–690.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0265813516683188>

- Kirkby, P., Williams, C., & Huq, S. (2015). A brief overview of Community-Based Adaptation. *International Centre for Climate Change and Development*.
- Kirkby, P., Williams, C., & Huq, S. (2017). Community-based adaptation (CBA): Adding conceptual clarity to the approach, and establishing its principles and challenges. *Climate and Development, 10*(7), 577–589. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2017.1372265>
- McGray, H., Hammill, A., Bradley, R., & Schipper, L., Parry, Jo-Ellen. (2007). *Weathering the storm: Options for framing adaptation and development*.
- McNamara, K. E., & Buggy, L. (2017). Community-based climate change adaptation: A review of academic literature. *Local Environment, 22*(4), 443–460. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2016.1216954>
- Mehrotra, S., Bardhan, R., & Ramamritham, K. (2018). Urban Informal Housing and Surface Urban Heat Island Intensity: Exploring Spatial Association in the City of Mumbai. *Environment and Urbanization ASIA, 9*(2), 158–177. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0975425318783548>
- Nay, J. J., Abkowitz, M., Chu, E., Gallagher, D., & Wright, H. (2014). A review of decision-support models for adaptation to climate change in the context of development. *Climate and Development, 6*(4), 357–367. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2014.912196>
- Ouzzani, M., Hammady, H., Fedorowicz, Z., & Elmagarmid, A. (2016). *Rayyan, Intelligent Systematic Review*. <https://www.rayyan.ai/>
- Piggott-McKellar, A. E., McNamara, K. E., Nunn, P. D., & Watson, J. E. M. (2019). What are the barriers to successful community-based climate change adaptation? A review of grey literature. *Local Environment, 24*(4), 374–390. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2019.1580688>
- Power, D. J. (2002). *Decision Support Systems: Concepts and Resources for Managers*. Greenwood Publishing Group.
- Rashid, A. K. M. M., & Khan, M. R. (2013). Community Based Adaptation: Theory and Practice. In R. Shaw, F. Mallick, & A. Islam (Eds.), *Climate Change Adaptation Actions in Bangladesh* (pp. 341–362). Springer Japan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-4-431-54249-0_18
- Regmi, B. R., & Star, C. (2014). Identifying operational mechanisms for mainstreaming community-based adaptation in Nepal. *Climate and Development, 6*(4), 306–317. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2014.977760>
- Regmi, B. R., Star, C., & Leal Filho, W. (2016). An overview of the opportunities and challenges of promoting climate change adaptation at the local level: A case study from a community adaptation planning in Nepal. *Climatic Change, 138*(3–4), 537–550. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-016-1765-3>
- Reid, H., Alam, M., Berger, R., Cannon, T., Huq, S., & Milligan, A. (Eds.). (2009). *Community-based adaptation to climate change: An overview* (Vol. 60).
- Remling, E., & Veitayaki, J. (2016). Community-based action in Fiji’s Gau Island: A model for the Pacific? *International Journal of Climate Change Strategies and Management, 8*(3), 375–398. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCCSM-07-2015-0101>
- Roy, R. (2018). Evaluating the Suitability of Community-Based Adaptation: A Case Study of Bangladesh. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-69838-0_3
- Sargeant, J. M., & O’Connor, A. M. (2020). Scoping Reviews, Systematic Reviews, and Meta-Analysis: Applications in Veterinary Medicine. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science, 7*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2020.00011>
- Satterthwaite, D., Archer, D., Colenbrander, S., Dodman, D., Hardoy, J., Mitlin, D., & Patel, S. (2020).

- Building Resilience to Climate Change in Informal Settlements. *One Earth*, 2(2), 143–156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2020.02.002>
- Simane, B., & Zaitchik, B. F. (2014). The sustainability of community-based adaptation projects in the Blue Nile Highlands of Ethiopia. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 6(7), 4308–4325. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su6074308>
- Spires, M., Shackleton, S., & Cundill, G. (2014). Barriers to implementing planned community-based adaptation in developing countries: A systematic literature review. *Climate and Development*, 6(3), 277–287. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2014.886995>
- Star, S. L., & Griesemer, J. R. (1989). Institutional Ecology, 'Translations' and Boundary Objects: Amateurs and Professionals in Berkeley's Museum of Vertebrate Zoology, 1907-39. *Social Studies of Science*, 19(3), 387–420. <https://doi.org/10.1177/030631289019003001>
- Tricco, A. C., Lillie, E., Zarin, W., O'Brien, K. K., Colquhoun, H., Levac, D., Moher, D., Peters, M. D. J., Horsley, T., Weeks, L., Hempel, S., Akl, E. A., Chang, C., McGowan, J., Stewart, L., Hartling, L., Aldcroft, A., Wilson, M. G., Garritty, C., ... Straus, S. E. (2018). PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and Explanation. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 169(7), 467–473. <https://doi.org/10.7326/M18-0850>
- Walker, B., Holling, C. S., Carpenter, S., & Kinzig, A. (2004). Resilience, Adaptability and Transformability in Social–ecological Systems. *Ecology and Society*, 9(2). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-00650-090205>
- Wang, J., Kuffer, M., Sliuzas, R., & Kohli, D. (2019). The exposure of slums to high temperature: Morphology-based local scale thermal patterns. *Science of The Total Environment*, 650, 1805–1817. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.09.324>
- Warrick, O. (2009). Ethics and methods in research for community-based adaptation: Reflections from rural Vanuatu. In *Community-based adaptation to climate change: An overview*. IIED.
- Westoby, R., McNamara, K. E., Kumar, R., & Nunn, P. D. (2020). From community-based to locally led adaptation: Evidence from Vanuatu. *AMBIO: A Journal of the Human Environment*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S13280-019-01294-8>
- Willems, J., Popering-Verkerk, J., & Eck, L. (2022). How boundary objects facilitate local climate adaptation networks: The cases of Amsterdam Rainproof and Water Sensitive Rotterdam. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09640568.2022.2030686>
- Williams, B. K. (2011). Adaptive management of natural resources—Framework and issues. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 92(5), 1346–1353. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2010.10.041>
- Williams, B. K., Szaro, R. C., & Shapiro, C. D. (2009). Adaptive management: The U.S. Department of the Interior technical guide. In *Adaptive management: The U.S. Department of the Interior technical guide* (p. 84) [Federal Government Series]. U.S. Department of the Interior. <http://pubs.er.usgs.gov/publication/70194537>

Appendix 1: List of 40 selected articles. Articles with casestudies are mentioned in bold

followed by non-casestudy articles

1. Antwi-Agyei, P., Dougill, A. J., & Stringer, L. C. (2015). **Barriers to climate change adaptation: Evidence from northeast Ghana in the context of a systematic literature review.** *Climate and Development*, 7(4), 297–309. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2014.951013>
2. Archer, D., Almansi, F., DiGregorio, M., Roberts, D., Sharma, D., & Syam, D. (2014). **Moving towards inclusive urban adaptation: Approaches to integrating community-based adaptation to climate change at city and national scale.** *Climate and Development*, 6(4), 345–356. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2014.918868>
3. Basel, B., Goby, G., & Johnson, J. (2020). **Community-based adaptation to climate change in villages of Western Province, Solomon Islands.** *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 156, 111266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2020.111266>
4. Beckwith, L. (2021). **No room to manoeuvre: Bringing together political ecology and resilience to understand community-based adaptation decision making.** *Climate and Development*, 0(0), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2021.1904811>
5. Chacko, J., Zobel, C. W., & Rees, L. P. (2018). **Challenges of Modeling Community-Driven Disaster Operations Management in Disaster Recurrent Areas: The Example of Portsmouth, Virginia.** 8.
6. Chaudhary, P., Thapa, K., Lamsal, K., Tiwari, P. R., & Chhetri, N. (2012). **Community-Based Climate Change Adaptation for Building Local Resilience in the Himalayas.** In *Human and Social Dimensions of Climate Change*. IntechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/50608>
7. Choko, O. P., Schmitt Olabisi, L., Onyeneke, R. U., Chiemela, S. N., Liverpool-Tasie, L. S. O., & Rivers, L. (2019). **A Resilience Approach to Community-Scale Climate Adaptation.** *Sustainability*, 11(11), 3100. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11113100>
8. Clissold, R., & McNamara, K. E. (2020). **Exploring local perspectives on the performance of a community-based adaptation project on Aniwa, Vanuatu.** *Climate and Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2019.1640656>
9. Dumaru, P. (2010). **Community-based adaptation: Enhancing community adaptive capacity in Druadrua Island, Fiji.** *WIREs Climate Change*, 1(5), 751–763. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.65>
10. Fox, A., Ziervogel, G., & Scheba, S. (2021). **Strengthening community-based adaptation for urban transformation: Managing flood risk in informal settlements in Cape Town.** *Local Environment*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2021.1923000>
11. Galvin, M. (2019). **Making Community-Based Adaptation a Reality: Different Conceptualisations, Different Politics.** *Human Geography*, 12(1), 50–63. <https://doi.org/10.1177/194277861901200104>
12. Guardaro, M., Messerschmidt, M., Hondula, D. M., Grimm, N. B., & Redman, C. L. (2020). **Building community heat action plans story by story: A three neighborhood case study.** *Cities*, 107, 102886. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2020.102886>
13. Huq, S., Yamin, F., Rahman, A., Chatterjee, A., Yang, X., Wade, S., Orindi, V., & Chigwada, J. (2009). **Linking Climate Adaptation and Development: A Synthesis of Six Case Studies from Asia and Africa.** *IDS Bulletin*, 36, 117–122. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1759->

14. Jamero, M. L., Onuki, M., Esteban, M., & Tan, N. (2018). Community-based adaptation in low-lying islands in the Philippines: Challenges and lessons learned | SpringerLink. Regional Environmental Change. <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.1007/s10113-018-1332-8>
15. Karim, Md. R., & Thiel, A. (2017). Role of community based local institution for climate change adaptation in the Teesta riverine area of Bangladesh. *Climate Risk Management*, 17, 92–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crm.2017.06.002>
16. Khezri, A., Bennett, R., & Zevenbergen, J. (2018). Defining the Requirements of an Information System for Climate Change Adaptation in the Mountain Communities of Dolakha, Nepal. *Climate*, 6(2), 47. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cli6020047>
17. Kim, D., & Kang, J. E. (2018). Integrating climate change adaptation into community planning using a participatory process: The case of Saebat Maeul community in Busan, Korea. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, 45(4), 669–690. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0265813516683188>
18. Lasage, R., Muis, S., Sardella, C. S. E., Van Drunen, M. A., Verburg, P. H., & Aerts, J. C. J. H. (2015). A Stepwise, Participatory Approach to Design and Implement Community Based Adaptation to Drought in the Peruvian Andes. *Sustainability*, 7(2), 1742–1773. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su7021742>
19. McNamara, K. E., Clissold, R., Westoby, R., Piggott-McKellar, A. E., Kumar, R., Clarke, T., Namoumou, F., Areki, F., Joseph, E., Warrick, O., & Nunn, P. D. (2020). An assessment of community-based adaptation initiatives in the Pacific Islands. *Nature Climate Change*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/S41558-020-0813-1>
20. Murtinho, F. (2016). What facilitates adaptation? An analysis of community-based adaptation to environmental change in the Andes. *International Journal of the Commons*, 10(1), 119–141. <https://doi.org/10.18352/ijc.585>
21. Rashid, A. K. M. M., & Khan, M. R. (2013). Community Based Adaptation: Theory and Practice. In R. Shaw, F. Mallick, & A. Islam (Eds.), *Climate Change Adaptation Actions in Bangladesh* (pp. 341–362). Springer Japan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-4-431-54249-0_18
22. Regmi, B. R., & Star, C. (2014). Identifying operational mechanisms for mainstreaming community-based adaptation in Nepal. *Climate and Development*, 6(4), 306–317. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2014.977760>
23. Regmi, B. R., Star, C., & Leal Filho, W. (2016). An overview of the opportunities and challenges of promoting climate change adaptation at the local level: A case study from a community adaptation planning in Nepal. *Climatic Change*, 138(3–4), 537–550. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-016-1765-3>
24. Reid, H., Alam, M., Berger, R., Cannon, T., Huq, S., & Milligan, A. (Eds.). (2009). Community-based adaptation to climate change: An overview (Vol. 60).
25. Remling, E., & Veitayaki, J. (2016). Community-based action in Fiji’s Gau Island: A model for the Pacific? *International Journal of Climate Change Strategies and Management*, 8(3), 375–398. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCCSM-07-2015-0101>
26. Roy, R. (2018). *Evaluating the Suitability of Community-Based Adaptation: A Case Study of Bangladesh*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-69838-0_3
27. Schaer, C. (2015). Condemned to live with one’s feet in water? A case study of community based strategies and urban maladaptation in flood prone Pikine/Dakar, Senegal. *Internation-*

tional Journal of Climate Change Strategies and Management, 7(4), 534–551.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCCSM-03-2014-0038>

28. Simane, B., & Zaitchik, B. F. (2014). The sustainability of community-based adaptation projects in the Blue Nile Highlands of Ethiopia. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 6(7), 4308–4325. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su6074308>
29. Westoby, R., McNamara, K. E., Kumar, R., & Nunn, P. D. (2020). From community-based to locally led adaptation: Evidence from Vanuatu. *AMBIO: A Journal of the Human Environment*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S13280-019-01294-8>
30. Ayers, J., & Forsyth, T. (2009). Community-Based Adaptation to Climate Change. *Environment: Science and Policy for Sustainable Development*, 51(4), 22–31. <https://doi.org/10.3200/ENV.51.4.22-31>
31. Dodman, D., & Mitlin, D. (2013). Challenges for Community-Based Adaptation: Discovering the Potential for Transformation. *Journal of International Development*, 25(5), 640–659. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jid.1772>
32. Faulkner, L., Ayers, J., & Huq, S. (2015). Meaningful Measurement for Community-Based Adaptation. *New Directions for Evaluation*, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ev.20133>
33. Forsyth, T. (2013). Community-based adaptation: A review of past and future challenges. *WIREs Climate Change*, 4(5), 439–446. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.231>
34. Forsyth, T. (2017). Community-Based Adaptation to Climate Change. *Climate Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ACREFORE/9780190228620.013.602>
- 35.* Khan, A. S. (2017). COREDAR for Cities: Developing a Capacity Building Tool for Sea-Level Rise Risk Communication and Urban Community-Based Adaptation. In W. Leal Filho & J. M. Keenan (Eds.), *Climate Change Adaptation in North America: Fostering Resilience and the Regional Capacity to Adapt* (pp. 137–157). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-53742-9_9
- 36.* Keenan (Eds.), *Climate Change Adaptation in North America: Fostering Resilience and the Regional Capacity to Adapt* (pp. 137–157). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-53742-9_9
37. Kirkby, P., Williams, C., & Huq, S. (2017). Community-based adaptation (CBA): Adding conceptual clarity to the approach, and establishing its principles and challenges. *Climate and Development*, 10(7), 577–589. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2017.1372265>
38. Leiter, T. (2016). Key considerations for monitoring and evaluation of community-based adaptation to climate change: Lessons from experience. In *enhancing adaptation to climate change in developing countries through community-based adaptation* (p. 17). African Centre for Technology Studies Press.
39. McNamara, K. E., & Buggy, L. (2017). Community-based climate change adaptation: A review of academic literature. *Local Environment*, 22(4), 443–460. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2016.1216954>
40. Piggott-McKellar, A. E., McNamara, K. E., Nunn, P. D., & Watson, J. E. M. (2019). What are the barriers to successful community-based climate change adaptation? A review of grey literature. *Local Environment*, 24(4), 374–390. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2019.1580688>
41. Spires, M., Shackleton, S., & Cundill, G. (2014). Barriers to implementing planned community-based adaptation in developing countries: A systematic literature review. *Climate and Development*, 6(3), 277–287. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2014.886995>

* Formatting issue: Citation 36 is part of citation 35 and the total number of reviewed paper is 40.

The complete citation no. 35 is: Khan, A.S., 2017. COREDAR for Cities: Developing a Capacity Building Tool for Sea-Level Rise Risk Communication and Urban Community-Based Adaptation, in: Leal Filho, W., Keenan, J.M. (Eds.), *Climate Change Adaptation in North America: Fostering Resilience and the Regional Capacity to Adapt*, Climate Change Management. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 137–157. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-53742-9_9.